

DESIGNING GEODETIC MONITORING NETWORKS: ASSESSING MINIMAL DETECTABLE DISPLACEMENT (MDD) WITH CONFIDENCE AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

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Accuracy and sensitivity criteria are commonly used in the pre-analysis of geodetic monitoring networks. While the accuracy ensures positional quality, the sensitivity analysis measures the network's ability to detect displacements. According to [1] both approaches can be presented as ellipsoids. The axes of these ellipsoids can be computed through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Minimal Detectable Displacements (MDD) [2,3,4]. The relationship between both ellipsoids only concerns to a size comparison due to a lack of theoretical basis. This condition also applies to the significance tests of computed displacements, where sensitivity characteristics are not considered. Thus, [1] provide a theoretical foundation that uniquely joint sensitivity with confidence and significance analysis. The approach outlined by [1] determines the sizes of significance, sensitivity, and confidence ellipsoids using MDD values and considers the inequality that involve the critical displacement values $u_{h,0}$ and the noncentrality parameter $\lambda_{h,\alpha_0,\beta_0}$. In particular, this approach coordinates the h –dimensional displacement vector with probability levels, including the significance level or Type I error rate (α_0), the false negative or Type II error rate (β_0), and the test's power ($\gamma_0 = 1 - \beta_0$). The main difference between accuracy (significance or confidence) and sensitivity ellipsoids is that the former disregards the probability of false negatives (β_0). Thus, for a specific value Type II error rate (β_0), called coordinate value of Type II error ($\underline{\beta_0}$) which depends of the h –dimensional displacement vector and α_0 , the inequality mentioned above becomes the equality $u_{h,0} = \lambda_{h,\alpha_0,\underline{\beta_0}}$. Here, setting $\alpha_0 = 1 - CL$ (where CL denotes the confidence level) reduces the analysis to two ellipsoids: confidence and sensitivity. Therefore, under this approach the MDD measures depends on variables related to the statistic test, such as h, α_0, β_0 . However, the research of [1] does not analyze aspects such as the network spatial dimension (1D, 2D, 3D), functional model, or their role in the pre-analysis or design of geodetic monitoring networks. Thus, this work presents an analysis of these aspects under the unified approach of [1], focusing on the design of geodetic monitoring networks and extending the findings of [5]. Thus, three experiments are presented: an analysis of the spatial dimension of the network, the influence of functional model and an example of GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) monitoring network design. For all analyzed networks, the inner constraint solution for datum definition was used [6]. To assess the effect of network spatial dimension, we analyzed a (linear) 1D leveling network (10 points), a (linearized) 2D triangulation network (6 points), and a (linear) 3D GNSS network (4 points), all with $h = rank(C_{\hat{d}}) = 9$, where $C_{\hat{d}}$ is the covariance matrix of the vector of displacements \hat{d} (Figure 1). Linear observations had a standard deviation of 1 mm, and angular observations in the 2D network had a standard deviation of 2.1 arc seconds (equivalent to linear standard deviation of 1 mm in sight distances of 100 m). Global MDD values used a significance level of $\alpha_0 = 5\%$, with $\underline{\beta_0} = 16\%$ for confidence analysis and $\beta_0 = 4\%$ or $\beta_0 = 20\%$ for sensitivity analysis (Table 1). We also analyzed networks with more points, all with $rank(C_{\hat{d}}) = 21$ (Figure 2), using $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $\underline{\beta_0} = 4\%$ for confidence analysis and $\beta_0 = 16\%$ or $\beta_0 = 20\%$ for sensitivity analysis (Table 2). To evaluate the network's functional model, we examined the 2D networks from previous experiments ("Case I") with a significance level of $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $\underline{\beta_0} = 20\%$ for sensitivity analysis (Figures 3 and 4). We considered a linearized model based on coordinate differences ("Case II") with Δx and Δy having a standard deviation of 1 mm. Networks with low and high redundancy were analyzed, with results in Tables 3 and 4 for 2D networks with 6 and 12 points, respectively. An analysis included a 2D trilateration network, a 2D

triangulation network, and a 3D GNSS network (Figure 5), all with $h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$. Points were fully interconnected in trilateration and GNSS networks, with maximum redundancy. Note that the triangulation network has the same number of redundant observations as the trilateration network. Global MDD values were analyzed with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $\beta_0 = 16\%$ for confidence and $\beta_0 = 20\%$ for sensitivity analysis (Table 5). Finally, we designed a simulated GNSS network with 6 points (Figure 6), aiming for local MDD values not exceeding 20 mm (with $h = 3$). The approach presented by [7] was used to obtain a realistic a priori covariance matrix, considering precise ephemeris. We analyzed two variables: time span (1h or 2h) and the number of baselines per point (Figure 8). The significance level was $\alpha_0 = 5\%$, with $\beta_0 = 36\%$ for confidence analysis and $\beta_0 = 20\%$ or $\beta_0 = 5\%$ for sensitivity analysis (Table 6). With 5 independent baselines per session, optimal cost solutions to meet the 20 mm threshold are in Table 7. From Tables 1 and 2, the max MDD values are more affected than the min MDD values. As the spatial dimension of the network increases, the max MDD value decreases for a given $h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}})$. However, the min MDD values are equal for 1D and 3D networks, larger than those of 2D networks. This is because the 2D network has a nonlinear mathematical model with different units (angles and distances). When linearizing the 2D network model to match the 1D and 3D models, the min MDD values equalize. Differences in max MDD values between networks of different dimensions increase with h . For example, at $h = 9$ and $\beta_0 = 20\%$, the difference between max MDD values for 1D and 3D networks is 5.1 mm (Table 1); at $h = 21$ and $\beta_0 = 20\%$, it increases to 14.5 mm (Table 2). From Tables 3 and 4, Cases I and II have the same max MDD values with low redundancy. However, for high redundancy, max MDD values are lower and min MDD values are higher for Case II compared to Case I. Although hypothetical for 2D networks, Case II shows that the functional model influences MDD values. For networks with linear models like leveling (1D) and GNSS (3D) networks, min and max MDD values are equal when observations have equal precision and all points are interconnected. In nonlinear models like trilateration, max MDD values are higher than min MDD values. Removing six distances and adding six angles in trilateration networks reduces max MDD values, but min and max MDD values remain different, making trilateration less effective for displacement detection compared to triangulation, even with the same number of redundant observations. From Tables 6 and 7, we find that 20 mm displacements can be detected within 3 hours (with a Type II error probability of around 36%) and 6 hours (with a Type II error probability of around 5%). It shows a direct relationship between time span and Type II error probability for GNSS monitoring network design. The main conclusions of this work are as follows: Larger network dimensions result in smaller max MDD values for a given $h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}})$. The differences in max MDD values between networks of different dimensions increase with h in both confidence and sensitivity analyses. Increasing redundancy is more efficient for 1D networks, which typically have higher max MDD values than 3D networks. It highlights the practical importance of considering both absolute MDD values and false negative probability in the pre-analysis of geodetic monitoring networks.

Figure 1 – equal h –dimensional networks ($h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$): I correspond to a 1D leveling network, II corresponds to a 2D horizontal network and III corresponds to a 3D GNSS network.

Source: Author (2024).

Figure 2 – equal h –dimensional networks ($h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}}) = 21$): I correspond to a 1D leveling network, II corresponds to a 2D horizontal network and III corresponds to a 3D GNSS network.

Source: Author (2024).

Figure 3 – A and B correspond to a 2D network of “Case I” with low and high redundancy (respectively), C and D correspond to a 2D network of “Case II” with low and high redundancy (respectively), $h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$ in all cases.

Source: Author (2024).

Figure 4 – A and B correspond to a 2D network of “Case I” with low and high redundancy (respectively), C and D correspond to a 2D network of “Case II” with low and high redundancy (respectively), $h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}}) = 21$ in all cases.

Source: Author (2024).

Figure 5 – I correspond to a 2D trilateration network, II corresponds to a 2D triangulation network and III corresponds to a 3D GNSS network, $h = \text{rank}(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$ in all cases.

Source: Author (2024).

Figure 6 – GNSS monitoring network with 3, 4 and 5 connections per point.

Source: Author (2024).

Table 1 – MDD values (mm) for geodetic networks (global analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$).

Spatial dimension	Sensitivity ($\beta_0 = 4\%$)		Confidence ($\beta_0 = 16\%$)		Sensitivity ($\beta_0 = 20\%$)	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
1D	4.4	14.4	2.9	9.4	2.8	9.1
2D	2.5	8.9	1.7	5.8	1.6	5.6
3D	4.4	6.3	2.9	4.1	2.8	4.0

Source: Author (2024).

Table 2 – MDD values (mm) for geodetic networks (global analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 21$).

Spatial dimension	Confidence ($\beta_0 = 4\%$)		Sensitivity ($\beta_0 = 16\%$)		Sensitivity ($\beta_0 = 20\%$)	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
1D	4.0	28.4	3.6	24.9	3.3	23.0
2D	2.1	15.6	1.8	13.6	1.7	12.6
3D	4.0	10.6	3.6	9.2	3.3	8.5

Source: Author (2024).

Table 3 – MDD values (mm) for 2D horizontal networks (global analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$, $\beta_0 = 20\%$, and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$).

Approach	Case I		Case II	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
Low redundancy	1.6	5.6	2.8	5.6
High redundancy	1.3	3.0	2.3	2.3

Source: Author (2024).

Table 4 – MDD values (mm) for 2D horizontal networks (global analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$, $\beta_0 = 20\%$, and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 21$).

Approach	Case I		Case II	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
Low redundancy	1.7	12.6	3.3	12.6
High redundancy	1.0	2.6	1.9	1.9

Source: Author (2024).

Table 5 – MDD values (mm) for geodetic networks of Figure 5 (global analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 9$)

Approach	Trilateration 2D		Triangulation 2D		GNSS 3D	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
Confidence ($\beta_0 = 16\%$)	2.5	5.6	1.8	4.4	2.9	2.9
Sensitivity ($\beta = 20\%$)	2.4	5.4	1.7	4.2	2.8	2.8

Source: Author (2024).

Table 6 – Maximum MDD values (mm) for GNSS monitoring network (local analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 3$)

Connections Per point	Time session: 1 hour			Time session: 2 hours		
	Confidence ($\beta_0 = 36\%$)	Sensitivity ($\beta = 20\%$)	Sensitivity ($\beta = 5\%$)	Confidence ($\beta_0 = 36\%$)	Sensitivity ($\beta = 20\%$)	Sensitivity ($\beta = 5\%$)
3	24.0	28.4	35.6	<u>16.8</u>	<u>19.9</u>	24.9
4	<u>20.0</u>	23.7	29.7	<u>14.0</u>	<u>16.5</u>	20.8
5	<u>17.6</u>	20.8	26.1	<u>12.3</u>	<u>14.5</u>	<u>18.2</u>

Source: Author (2024).

Table 7 – Optimal solutions for the GNSS monitoring network with a threshold of 20 mm for MDD values (local analysis with $\alpha_0 = 5\%$ and $h = rank(C_{\hat{a}}) = 3$)

Confidence ($\beta_0 = 36\%$)	Sensitivity ($\beta = 20\%$)	Sensitivity ($\beta = 5\%$)
5 connections per point and 3 sessions with 1 hour each (3 hours in total)	3 connections per point and 2 sessions with 2 hours each (4 hours in total)	5 connections per point and 3 sessions with 2 hours each (6 hours in total)

Source: Author (2024).

Key words: Minimal Detectable Displacement (MDD), geodetic network design, sensitivity analysis, displacements significance test, confidence regions, Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

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